

Study On Knowledge, Attitude And Practices Of Contraceptive Methods Among Women Of Reproductive Age Group Of Tribal Community In A Western District (Sambalpur) Of Odisha, India: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Tribal communities often face socio-cultural barriers in accessing reproductive healthcare services, particularly modern contraceptive methods. Understanding the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding contraception among women in these communities is critical for developing effective family planning interventions. This study was undertaken to assess the KAP regarding contraceptive methods among reproductive-age women in a tribal community in a Sambalpur district present in western part of Odisha. The findings aim to inform targeted interventions to increase awareness and acceptance of contraception in similar underprivileged populations. **Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional and descriptive study conducted among 785 women aged 15–49 years in a tribal-dominated blocks of Sambalpur district November 2022 to December 2023. The region comprises primarily rural and remote areas with limited access to healthcare services. The study focused on assessing the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) related to contraceptive methods among women of reproductive age residing in tribal communities. A structured questionnaire assessed their knowledge, attitudes, and contraceptive practices. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** Out of 785 women interviewed, the majority (44%) were aged 25–35 years, with 68.9% being unemployed and 93.2% belonging to lower socio-economic status. Awareness about contraceptive methods was reported by 86% of participants. Among those aware (n=675), the most commonly known methods were oral pills (68%) and condoms (66%). However, only 61.1% had ever used contraception and just 23.8% were current users, with condoms (53.6%) and oral pills (31.1%) being the most used. Fear of side effects (51.4%) and partner opposition (20.6%) were major reasons for non-use. Statistically significant associations were found between knowledge/practice and factors such as age, education, occupation, religion, marital status, and number of children ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Though awareness is relatively high, the gap between knowledge and practice remains due to cultural, educational, and accessibility challenges. Tailored health education and community engagement are essential to improve uptake.

Keywords: Contraceptive methods, Tribal women, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Reproductive health

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INTRODUCTION

Family planning plays a pivotal role in reducing maternal and infant mortality and in achieving sustainable population growth. [1] Contraceptive methods empower women to control their fertility, plan pregnancies, and participate fully in social and economic life. [2] However, despite widespread availability of modern contraceptive options, their uptake remains low among certain populations, particularly in tribal communities. [3]

India is home to over 104 million tribal people, constituting about 8.6% of the total population. [4] These communities often inhabit remote and rural areas with limited access to healthcare services, education, and socio-economic development programs. [5] The National Family Health Survey (NFHS-4) reported significant disparities in contraceptive use between tribal and non-tribal populations, with tribal women demonstrating

lower knowledge and utilization rates. [6] Several factors contribute to this gap, including illiteracy, poverty, patriarchal social structures, and cultural taboos surrounding contraception. [7]

In many tribal societies, fertility is closely tied to cultural identity, with larger families viewed as symbols of prosperity and security. [8] Furthermore, decisions about family planning are often male-dominated, limiting women's autonomy over reproductive choices. [9] Health workers have reported that tribal women frequently express fear of side effects, religious concerns, or misinformation related to sterilization or hormonal contraceptives. [10] These attitudes reflect the urgent need for culturally sensitive, community-based education strategies. [11]

Previous studies conducted in tribal areas of central and eastern India have highlighted a wide variation in knowledge and practice of contraceptive methods. [12] For instance, a study in Madhya Pradesh revealed that while 60% of tribal women had heard of family planning methods, only 35% used any contraception. [13] Similarly, in Odisha, lack of access to health facilities and low female literacy rates were associated with poor contraceptive prevalence. [14]

Additionally, health infrastructure challenges, such as understaffed primary health centers (PHCs), limited outreach, and inadequate counselling services, further restrict access to modern contraception in tribal belts. [15] The government has introduced several schemes under the National Health Mission to target vulnerable groups, yet implementation remains inconsistent across districts. [16] Furthermore, language barriers and a lack of trust in healthcare providers often discourage tribal women from seeking reproductive health services. [17]

Understanding the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) of tribal women toward contraceptive use is crucial for designing interventions that address not only access but also sociocultural barriers. [18] By identifying these gaps, healthcare policymakers and providers can tailor strategies to improve awareness and enhance service delivery in tribal regions. [19]

Effective family planning among tribal populations can significantly contribute to improved maternal health, child survival, and women's empowerment. [20]

This study was undertaken to assess the KAP regarding contraceptive methods among reproductive-age women in a tribal community in Sambalpur district situated in western part of Odisha. The findings aim to inform targeted interventions to increase awareness and acceptance of contraception in similar underprivileged populations. [21]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a community-based cross-sectional descriptive study conducted in a tribal-dominated areas of Sambalpur district in western India between November 2022 and December 2023. The region comprises primarily rural and remote areas with limited access to healthcare services. The study focused on assessing the knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) related to contraceptive methods among women of reproductive age residing in tribal communities.

Study Population

The study population included women aged 15–49 years who were currently residing in the selected tribal areas for at least six months prior to the survey.

Sampling Technique

A multistage random sampling method was employed. First, three blocks were randomly selected from the district. Then, two villages from each block were randomly chosen. In each village, systematic random sampling was used to select eligible women until the sample size was achieved

Sample Size

A sample size of 384 was calculated using the formula:

$$n = Z^2pq/d^2$$

(Assuming a prevalence (p) of 50%, 95% confidence interval (Z = 1.96), and margin of error (d) of 5%)

As a multistage random sampling method was employed the calculated sample size was multiplied by 2 (Design effect), so that the sample

remains representative and the results are statistically valid.

So Total Sample size = $384 \times 2 = 768$

After addition of probable non responder of 5% the absolute sample size was: 806 (rounded to 810)

After data collection 785 response were found complete in all respect and hence these 785 were included in the analysis.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 15–49 years
- Residents of the selected tribal villages for at least 6 months
- Willing to provide informed consent
- Currently married (as contraceptive use was assessed in the context of marital status)
- Exclusion Criteria
- Women who were severely ill or mentally challenged at the time of the survey
- Pregnant women (to prevent bias in assessing current contraceptive use)
- Those unwilling to participate or unable to communicate effectively

Data Collection Tool

A structured and pretested questionnaire was used to collect data. The questionnaire was developed in English and translated into the local tribal dialect, ensuring clarity and cultural appropriateness. It comprised four sections:

1. Socio-demographic details (age, education, occupation, family type, number of children, etc.)
2. Knowledge of contraceptive methods (awareness, sources of information, types known)

3. Attitude (beliefs, perceptions about safety, effectiveness, social acceptability)

4. Practices (use of contraception, reasons for use or non-use, method used)

The tool was validated through a pilot study in a non-study tribal village, and modifications were made based on feedback.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected by trained female health workers under supervision. House-to-house visits were conducted, and face-to-face interviews were carried out after obtaining informed consent. Privacy and confidentiality were strictly maintained. Each interview took approximately 30–40 minutes

Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and verbal and written consent was obtained. Participation was voluntary, and respondents could withdraw at any point without any consequences.

Data Analysis

Collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Descriptive statistics such as percentages and means were used to summarize the data. Chi-square test was used to assess associations between socio-demographic variables and contraceptive practices. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 785 women were interviewed. The findings have been categorized into socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to contraceptive methods.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of Participants (n=785)

	Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	(15–25)	204	26
	(25–35)	345	44
	(35–49)	236	30
Education	Illiterate	84	10.7
	Primary education	137	17.5
	Middle School Certificate	384	48.9
	High school certificate	64	8.2
	Intermediate/ITI/Diploma	81	10.3
	Graduate	34	4.3

	Professional/ Honours	1	0.1
Occupation	Unemployed	541	68.9
	Elementary occupation	188	23.9
	Plant or Machine operators	0	0.0
	Crafts or related trade works	47	6.0
	Skilled Agricultural /Fishery workers	0	0.0
	Shop and market sales workers	0	0.0
	clerks	9	1.1
	Technicians and associated professional	0	0.0
	Professionals	0	0.0
	Legislators, Senior officials, Managers	0	0.0
Socio-economic status	Upper	0	0.0
	Upper middle	0	0.0
	Lower middle	1	0.1
	Upper lower	52	6.6
	Lower	732	93.2
Religion (Practising)	Hindu	334	42.5
	Muslim	79	10.1
	Christian	207	26.4
	Don't wants to share	165	21.0
Number of Children in The family	No children	69	8.8
	1	241	30.7
	2	284	36.2
	3	124	15.8
	More Than 3	67	8.5
Marital status	Single	148	18.9
	Married	533	67.9
	Widowed	59	7.5
	Separated	43	5.5
	Divorced	2	0.3
Number of Years of Marriage	Not married	39	5.0
	Less Than 1 year	179	22.8
	1- 5 years	142	18.1
	5-10 years	165	21.0
	more than 10 years	260	33.1
Types of Family women is currently residing with	Nuclear	204	26.0
	Joint	154	19.6
	Three Generation Family	427	54.4

Table 1 describe the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. Majority (44%) of women were in the 25–35 age group, 30% and 26% respondents were belonged to 35-49 yrs, & 15-25 years of age group respectively. Most (48.9%) of the respondents were studied up to middle school certificate, followed by 17.5% were having only primary education. Only 10.3% were found to have completed intermediate/Diploma/ITI. Out of the 785 respondents only 10.7% were found not having any formal education. Out of the 785 respondents 68.9% were housewife not engaged in formal income generating activities. Only 23.9% were found engaged in elementary occupation followed by 6% who were engaged in craft related activities. Around 93.2% respondents were belonged to lower socio-economic class family as per the modified Kuppaswamy classification followed by 6.6%, who were in Upper Lower socio-economy class family category. Most of the respondents were Hindu (42.5%) followed by Christian (26.4%) and Muslims (10.1%). There were 21% respondents who hesitate to share their religious practices. There were 8.8% respondents having no living children at the time of survey, followed by 15.8%, 30.7%, 36.2% were having 3(three), 1(One), 2(Two) numbers of living children respectively. 8.5% were found having more than 3 living children. Most (67.9%) of the respondents were married. Whereas 18.9%, 7.5%, 5.5%, 0.3% were single, widowed, separated, Divorces respectively. While 5% respondents were not married at the time of survey, 33.1% were having married for 10 & more years. 22.8% were having married in the last 1 year. Around 54.4% respondents were living in three

generation family that is along with her in laws and children, followed by 26% & 19.6% living in nuclear and joint family respectively.

Table 2: Awareness about Contraceptives among women of reproductive age group (n=785)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	675	86
No	110	14

According to Table 2 out of the 785 respondents 675 (86%) had awareness regarding contraceptives practices.

Table 3: Knowledge about contraceptives among women of Reproductive age group (n=675)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
a. Awareness of Different Contraceptives Methods¹ (n=675)		
Oral contraceptive pills	459	68
Copper-T/IUD	351	52
Condoms	446	66
Injectable contraceptives	142	21
Permanent sterilization	385	57
Natural/Traditional methods	216	32
b. Knows where to get contraceptives² (n=675)		
Government hospital	444	65.8
Private hospital	76	11.2
Chemist	194	28.7
ASHA	482	71.4
AWW	207	30.7
MPHW(F)	556	82.3
Others	7	1.1
c. Knowledge regarding Ideal spacing period(year) (n=675)		
<1	51	7.6
1-2	247	36.6
3-4	296	43.8
5 and above	18	2.7
Don't Know	63	9.3
d. Knowledge regarding Fertile Period (n=675)		
During Menstruation	130	19.2
Immediately after Menstruation	174	25.8
In the Middle of the cycle	76	11.3
Just Before menstruation	101	14.9
Anytime	61	9.1
Don't know	133	19.7
e. Knowledge of Side effects of contraception³ (n=675)		
Headaches	28	4.2
Vomiting	152	22.5
Dizziness	223	33.1
Cessation of Menstruation	124	18.3
Irregular menstruation	439	65.1
Heavy menstruation	265	39.2
Increased vaginal discharge	40	5.9
Vaginal infection	11	1.7
Weight Gain	111	16.4
f. Source of Information⁴ (n=675)		
ASHA/ANM workers	447	66.2
Radio/TV	165	24.5
Friends/Relatives	236	34.9
Posters/Leaflets	61	9

^{1,2,3,4} Multiple responses allowed for the respondents.

Table 3 describe the knowledge of Tribal women of reproductive age group on contraceptive methods and their side effects. Out of the 675 respondents who had any awareness about contraceptives, 68% & 66% were heard about OC pill & condoms respectively. Followed by Sterilization (57%), IUCD (52%), Natural;/ Traditional methods (32%). Respondents were least (only 21%) aware of Injectable contraceptives. When asked about the availability (where to get) of contraceptives, 82.3%, 71.4%, 65.8% were responded with MPHWF, ASHA, Government hospital respectively. At the same time 30.7%, 28.7%, 11.2% were mentioned that contraceptives were available at AWWs, Chemists, & Private hospitals respectively. When inquired about the "Ideal spacing period", 43.8%, 36.6% were responded with 3-4 years & 1-2 years respectively. Followed by 9.3%, who were no knowledge on Ideal spacing period. When asked about the "Fertile period" 25.8% responded with "immediately after menstruation" followed by 19.7%, who "didn't have knowledge" on fertile period. Whereas 19.2% responded with "during Menstruation", 9.3% answered that "anytime during the period". Most (65.1%) of the respondents labelled Irregular menstruation is the most common side effects of using contraception followed by Heavy menstruation (39.2%), Dizziness (33.1%), Vomiting (22.5%), Cessation of Menstruation (18.3%), Weight Gain (16.4%, Increased vaginal discharge (5.9%), Headache (4.2%). Most of the knowledge on contraceptive practices along with usages, availability, side effects, failure rate were from ASHA/ ANM workers (66.2%), followed by Friends / relatives. Mass media like Television/ radio/ internet acts as a reliable source of information for 34.9% respondents.

Table 4: Attitudes toward Contraceptive Use

Attitude Statement	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)
Contraceptives are safe	408(60.4)	267(39.6)
Contraceptive use leads to infertility	167(24.7)	508(75.3)
Husband's approval is necessary	547(81)	128(19)
Contraception is against cultural norms	109(16.1)	566(83.9)
Do you recommend contraception to family/friends	369(54.7)	306(45.3)

In table 4, Most (60.4%) of the respondents believed that contraceptives are safe for use but at the same time 24.7% were of the opinion that use of contraceptives causes infertility. A majority (81%) believed that husband's approval was essential for using of contraceptives. 16.1% women opined that use of contraceptives is against their cultural norm. 54.7% of the women responded that they are satisfied with the currently using contraceptives and will recommend the same to their friends & family.

Table 5: Practice of Contraception

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
a. Ever used contraception (n=675)		
Yes	412	61.1
No	263	38.9
b. Contraceptive methods ever Used (n=412)*		
Oral pills	229	55.6
Condoms	325	78.8
IUD	64	15.6
Sterilization	73	17.8
Others (natural, injectables)	9	2.2
c. Currently using contraception(n=675)		
Yes	161	23.8
no	514	76.2
d. Types currently using(n=161)*		
Oral contraceptive pills + Saheli	50	31.1
Condoms	86	53.6
Injectables + Mirena	3	1.9
Female sterilisation	25	15.6
Male sterilisation	1	0.6
IUCD	4	2.2
Traditional methods	3	1.9

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Any other Barrier methods	3	1.9
e. Ever had problem while using contraceptives (n= 161)		
Yes	39	24.3
no	122	75.7
f. Types of contraception that causes problem (n=161)*		
Oral contraceptive pills + Saheli	48	29.9
Condoms	55	34
Injectables + Mirena	85	52.9
Female sterilisation	28	17.3
Male sterilisation	19	11.8
IUCD	153	94.8
Traditional methods	3	2.03
Any other Barrier methods	20	12.3

*Multiple response allowed to the respondents

Table 5 described about the current practice of the surveyed population, regarding the uses of contraception. Out of the total 675 respondents who had some knowledge on contraception 61.1% were had ever used any type of contraception. Condoms were found to be the most (78.8%) commonly used methods followed by Oral pills (55.6%). Other methods like Female Sterilization, IUCD, Other natural methods were practiced by 17.8%, 15.6%, & 2.2% respectively. Only 23.8%, out of 675 were found currently using any type of contraceptive methods. Among the current users Condoms (53.6%), followed by Oral pills (31.1%) were found the most preferred methods. Other methods like Female sterilization, IUCD is practiced by 15.6%, 2.2% of the respondents. Injectables, Traditional methods, any other barrier methods were used by 1.9% each respondent. 24.3% of the respondent shared that they faced problem while using contraception. As per the respondent IUCD (94.8%), Injectables (52.9%) were the most common contraception causing problems, followed by condoms (34%) and OC pills (29.9%). Problems associated with Female sterilization, Male sterilization, and any other barrier methods were limited to 17.3%, 11.8%,12.3% respectively.

Table 6: Reasons for not using Contraceptives currently (n=514)*

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Don't know much about it	56	10.9
Cultural / religious belief	121	23.5
Opposition from Partner	106	20.6
Fear of Side Effects	264	51.4
Yet to complete family	117	22.8
Undecided	97	18.9
Others	165	32.1

*Multiple answer allowed to the respondents

Table 6 describe the reasons for currently not using any type of contraception. While 51.4% share their reservation of using contraception due to fear of side effects like infertility, irregular bleeding, heavy menstrual bleeding and other health problems. Followed by cultural taboo/ religious beliefs (23.5%), incomplete family (22.8%), Opposition from partner (20.6%), indecisiveness (18.9%), No knowledge/Awareness (10.9%), for not using contraception currently.

Table 7: Association of Knowledge on contraception with socio-demographic parameter.

Variables		Yes(675)(%)	No(110)(%)	
Age	(15–24)	183(89.7)	21(10.3)	Chi square value= 12.94, p value 0.0015
	(25–34)	305(88.4)	40(11.6)	
	(35–49)	187(79.2)	49(20.8)	
Education	illiterate	46(54.8)	38(45.2)	Chi square value= 96.415, p value 0.001
	Primary	110(80.3)	27(19.7)	
	Up to high school	403(90)	45(10)	
	More than high school	116(100)	0	

Occupation	Unemployed/ housewife	431(79.7)	110(20.3)	Chi square value= 57.69, p value 0.001
	Not unemployed	244(100)	0	
Socio-Economic Status	Upper	0	0	Chi square value= 9.262, p value 0.009
	Upper middle	0	0	
	Lower middle	1(100)	0	
	Upper lower	52(100)	0	
	Lower	622(85)	110(15)	
Religion	Hindu	310(92.8)	24(7.2)	Chi square value= 138.721, p value 0.001
	Muslim	34(43)	45(57)	
	Christian	189(91.3)	18(8.7)	
	Don't want to share	142(86.1)	23(13.9)	
Number of Children	No children	48(69.6)	21(30.4)	Chi square value= 4.055, p value 0.001
	1	217(90)	24(10)	
	2	250(88)	34(12)	
	3	93(75)	31(25)	
	More Than 3	67(100)	0	
Marital status	Single	137(92.6)	11(7.4)	Chi square value= 111.803, p value 0.001
	Married	471(88.4)	62(11.6)	
	Widowed	24(40.7)	35(59.3)	
	Separated	41(95.3)	2(4.7)	
	Divorced	2(100)	0	
Type of family	Nuclear	174(85.3)	30(14.7)	Chi square value= 5.046, p value 0.080
	Joint	141(91.6)	13(8.4)	
	Three Generation Family	360(84.3)	67(15.7)	

As per the table 7 it was found that knowledge on Contraception among tribal women of reproductive age group was found significantly associated with socio-demographic factors like age ($\chi^2= 12.94$, p value 0.0015), Education of the respondent ($\chi^2= 96.415$, p value 0.001), Occupation of the respondents ($\chi^2= 57.69$, p value 0.001), Socio-economic status of the family of the respondent ($\chi^2= 9.262$, p value 0.009), Religion ($\chi^2= 138.721$, p value 0.001), Number of living Children ($\chi^2= 4.055$, p value 0.001), Marital status ($\chi^2= 111.803$, p value 0.001).

Table 8: Association of Contraceptives Practices with other socio-demographic Parameters.

	Variables	Yes(412)(%)	No(263)(%)	
Age	(15–24)	112(61.2)	71(38.8)	Chi square value= 30.559, p value 0.001
	(25–34)	215(70.5)	90(29.5)	
	(35–49)	85(45.5)	102(54.5)	
Education	illiterate	0	46(100)	Chi square value= 111.988, p value 0.001
	Primary	45(40.9)	65(59.1)	
	Up to high school	289(71.7)	114(28.3)	
	More than high school	78(67.2)	38(32.8)	
Occupation	Unemployed/ housewife	294(68.2)	137(31.8)	Chi square value= 25.82, p value 0.001
	Not unemployed	118(48.4)	126(51.6)	
Socio-Economic Status	Upper	0	0	Chi square value= 0.106, p value 0.744
	Upper middle	0	0	
	Lower middle	1(100)	0	
	Upper lower	39(62.9)	23(37.1)	
	Lower	372(60.8)	240(39.2)	
Religion	Hindu	134(43.2)	176(56.8)	Chi square value= 175.72, p value 0.001
	Muslim	0	34(100)	
	Christian	171(90.5)	18(9.5)	
	Don't want to share	107(75.4)	35(24.6)	
Number of Children	No children	48(100)	0	Chi square value= 198.14, p value 0.001
	1	200(92.2)	17(7.8)	
	2	108(43.2)	142(56.8)	
	3	32(34.4)	61(65.6)	

	More Than 3	24(35.8)	43(64.2)	
Marital status	Single	137(100)	0	Chi square value= 186.62, p value 0.001
	Married	208(44.2)	263(55.8)	
	Widowed	24(100)	0	
	Separated	41(100)	0	
	Divorced	2(100)	0	
Type of family	Nuclear	92(52.9)	82(47.1)	Chi square value= 9.265, p value 0.009
	Joint	82(58.2)	59(41.8)	
	Three Generation Family	238(66.1)	122(33.9)	

As per the table 8 it was found that practices on Contraception among tribal women of reproductive age group was found significantly associated with socio-demographic factors like age ($\chi^2= 30.559$, p value 0.001), Education of the respondent ($\chi^2= 111.98$, p value 0.001), Occupation of the respondents ($\chi^2= 25.82$, p value 0.001), Religion ($\chi^2= 175.72$, p value 0.001), Number of living Children ($\chi^2= 198.14$, p value 0.001), Marital status ($\chi^2= 186.62$, p value 0.001).

DISCUSSION

This study explored the socio-demographic profile, knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding contraceptive use among tribal women of reproductive age in a tertiary care setting. The findings highlight significant gaps in both awareness and utilization of contraceptive methods, despite reasonable levels of knowledge among those exposed to health services.

A majority of the women (44%) were in the 25–35 years age group, with a high rate of unemployment (68.9%) and low educational attainment—only 4.3% being graduates. This demographic pattern is consistent with previous studies conducted in tribal and rural populations of India, where limited education and occupational opportunities are known barriers to reproductive health service utilization (Patel et al., 2011; Singh & Kaur, 2014) [22,23].

Awareness of contraception was relatively high at 86%, similar to NFHS-5 data which reports awareness rates above 80% among rural Indian women. [24] However, the actual use was lower: only 61.1% had ever used contraceptives, and just 23.8% were current users. The gap between knowledge and practice is consistent with previous research by Rajaram and Rashmi (2010), who observed that while tribal women may be aware of methods like condoms and pills, sociocultural norms and myths hinder actual usage. [25]

Among those who had knowledge, condoms (66%) and oral pills (68%) were the most known and used methods—reflecting national trends. However, awareness of long-term or less-visible

methods such as injectables (21%) and IUCDs (52%) was considerably lower. This aligns with findings from Puri et al. (2007), who noted that fear of side effects and lack of trust in newer methods limits uptake among tribal and less educated groups. [26]

The study revealed a strong reliance on community health workers like ASHAs and MPHWF for contraceptive knowledge. ASHAs were cited as sources by 66.2% of respondents—supporting earlier reports by Bhatnagar et al. (2015), which emphasized the pivotal role of ASHAs in family planning outreach in rural areas. [27] Mass media played a minor role (24.5%), indicating underutilization of broader IEC (Information, Education, Communication) strategies in tribal zones.

Attitudinally, while 60.4% believed contraceptives to be safe, 24.7% still associated them with infertility—a common myth also documented by Kumari and Sachdeva (2015). [28] Importantly, 81% of women felt the husband's approval was necessary, pointing to significant male dominance in reproductive decision-making—echoing studies from tribal belts in Odisha and Jharkhand (Gupta et al., 2013). [29]

Barriers to current usage were primarily fear of side effects (51.4%), cultural/religious beliefs (23.5%), and partner opposition (20.6%). Similar barriers were identified in studies by Dasgupta et al. (2012) and Baruah et al. (2014), which suggested that improving community sensitization

and male involvement can enhance contraceptive uptake. [30,31]

Statistically significant associations were found between contraceptive knowledge/practice and factors like age, education, religion, marital status, and number of children—mirroring findings by Pandey et al. (2018) and Deshmukh et al. (2020). [32,33]

In conclusion, while awareness is high, actual contraceptive use remains low among tribal women, driven by socio-cultural, informational, and gender-related barriers. Tailored interventions focusing on education, debunking myths, and enhancing male participation are crucial. Strengthening the role of frontline health workers and integrating mass media campaigns could further bridge the gap between knowledge and practice.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that although a considerable proportion of tribal women in the reproductive age group are aware of modern contraceptive methods, the actual practice remains significantly lower. Socio-cultural factors such as male-dominated decision-making, myths, and low educational attainment serve as major barriers to contraceptive use. The strong influence of community health workers as sources of information highlights an opportunity for targeted interventions. Increasing female education, enhancing community-based awareness programs, promoting male involvement, and delivering culturally sensitive reproductive counselling through trained personnel can improve family planning practices in tribal communities. Addressing these gaps is critical for improving maternal and child health outcomes and achieving national reproductive health goals.

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